

ECONOMYC DEVELOPMENT AND DEVELOPMENTS STRATEGIES

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada mamlakatimizda milliy iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari to'g'risida muallif tomonidan fikr mulohazalar keltirilgan. Qolaversa, iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari bo'yicha taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Annotation: In this article, the national economy in our country the author comments on the possibilities of development. In addition, proposals and recommendations on the directions of economic development have been developed.

Key words: national economy, currency relations, fiscal policy, automobile industry, agriculture.

Kalit so'zlar: milliy iqtisodiyot, valyuta munosablari, fiskal siyosat, avtomobilsozlik, qishloq xo'jaligi.

In our country, opportunities are being created for the fundamental development of all sectors and branches of the economy, and the development of our national economy by clearly defining the locomotive branches of the economy. The New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan presented by the President consists of seven directions, and it is significant because it is a continuation of the Strategy of Actions adopted 5 years ago and the successful reforms implemented within it. In particular, the third direction of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan - the priority tasks set in the direction of developing the national economy, its growth rates at the level of the requirements of the time, the continuation of the reforms initiated within the priority directions of economic development and liberalization of the action strategy reflects that it can be evaluated as It is this New Uzbekistan development strategy that is embodied as the regulatory and legal framework

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for the development of the national economy. It should also be said that effectively implemented reforms are a guarantee for the next success. There is also a special meaning in the fact that the priority task for 2022-2026 is to increase the volume of GDP per capita through the development of the real sector of the economy. In the past five years, i.e. in 2017-2021, within the framework of the Action Strategy, the leading industries (textiles, electrical engineering, automobile industry, building materials industry, chemical and petrochemical industry, agricultural machinery, energy, etc.) development strategies have been adopted. We see that this is also an opportunity to develop the national economy. of payment systems, the possibility of unlimited purchase of foreign currency, the problem of cash was solved, and the operation of automated ATMs was launched. was placed. As a result of the liberalization of foreign trade, the volume of foreign trade is increasing rapidly. After the liberalization of currency and foreign trade, the introduction of the principles of market mechanisms into the economy, the liberalization of prices and other related reforms, ensuring the stability of domestic prices in the country, keeping inflation at a low and stable level. revenues, and on the other hand, lead to effective spending of budget expenditures, and as a result, economic activity in the country will increase and macroeconomic stability will be ensured. Acceleration of economic reforms and successful implementation of development programs is considered a necessary criterion. It should be noted separately that low and stable indicators of inflation, ensuring balance in economic growth, production competitiveness and raising the standard of living of the population are important factors. From this point of view, reduction and stabilization of price growth rates should be one of the main goals of the state economic policy. Over the past 5 years, the policy of Uzbekistan in the fiscal sphere has changed radically, in particular, transparency and openness of the budget have been ensured, large-scale reforms have been implemented to simplify and improve taxation, and a number of effective measures have been implemented to reduce the share of the shadow economy. measures have been taken.

Also, the system of rational use of budget funds was improved, the role and place of the Oliy Majlis in the budget process was increased, the powers of the representative bodies of local authorities were expanded, and the "Initiative budget" project was launched. In addition, sovereign international bonds of the Republic of Uzbekistan were issued, and the proceeds were directed to the financing of projects of strategic importance for the prosperity of the country. In accordance with the development strategy, priority is given to the task of ensuring the stability of the budget and external debt in Uzbekistan in 2022-2026. The reason is that the increase in the country's fiscal deficit and the increase in foreign debts

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exceeding the standards set at the international level can certainly pose a threat to the national economy.

Also, this strategy envisages paying special attention to expanding the capabilities of local budgets in order to ensure effective spending of budget funds. These priority tasks set in the fiscal sphere are considered a logical continuation of the previous reforms, which, on the one hand, serve to rationally form budget revenues, and on the other hand, lead to effective spending of budget expenditures, and ultimately, economic activity in the country will increase and macroeconomic stability will be ensured.

In conclusion, it should be said that the new development strategy of Uzbekistan defines a number of strategic tasks for the further development of the country's economy in the next five years. In particular, special importance is attached to tasks related to further support of business activities, continuation of reforms on creation of business environment and necessary infrastructures, halving of poverty, development of regions and development of agrarian sector.

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